

To Study the Relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and General Intelligence of Undergraduate Students

Arju Panwar¹ and Shubhra Chaturvedi²

1. Professor, J.V. Jain College, Saharanpur, U.P.
2. M.Ed. Student, J.V. Jain College, Saharanpur, U.P.

Received : 11/02/2025

1st BPR : 20/02/2025

2nd BPR : 01/03/2025

Accepted : 14/03/2025

Abstract

This study investigates explores the level of Spiritual Intelligence and General Intelligence of undergraduate students. In the context of Undergraduate Students, both general intelligence and spiritual intelligence play crucial roles in shaping academic performance, social interactions and personal development, while general intelligence is often associated with academic success and problem-solving abilities. Data was gathered from a selected sample of 100 students across various colleges in Saharanpur. Test of General Intelligence for College Students by Dr. K.S.Misra and Dr. S.K.Pal and Test of Spiritual Intelligence by Prof. Roquiya Zainuddin and Ms. Anjum Ahmed was utilized to carry out the study. Pearson's correlation was utilized to analyze the data. The outcomes of the study are: (a) There is no significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and general intelligence of undergraduate male students. (b) There is significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and general intelligence of undergraduate female students.

Keywords: General Intelligence, Spiritual Intelligence, Data.

Introduction

In the context of Undergraduate Students, both general intelligence and spiritual intelligence play crucial roles in shaping academic performance, social interactions and personal development While general intelligence is often associated with academic success and problem-solving abilities. Spiritual intelligence is believed to influence personal well-being, ethical decision making and a sense of purpose. The concept of intelligence has long been a subject of academic inquiry, with researchers traditionally focusing on cognitive abilities such as problem solving, reasoning and memory often referred to as general intelligence. However, recent developments in psychology have expanded the definition of intelligence to include emotional and spiritual dimensions. Spiritual intelligence defined as the ability to apply spiritual values and principles to daily life, has gained increasing attention as a complementary aspect of a person's overall intelligence. This aspect challenges traditional framework and introduces a more holistic view of human potential, particularly in environments that require both cognitive and emotional adaptability, such as college.

Spiritual Intelligence : Spiritual Intelligence is the manifestation of inner spiritual traits using our thinking, deeds and point of view. With inner strength of brain and soul and its connection with existence in the universe, spiritual intelligence is used. Spiritual intelligence is our capacity to acquire an accurate and deep understanding of multiple levels of awareness. Spiritual intelligence enlarges our ability to understand others at the inmost level. Danah Zohar was the first physicist who devised the title "Spiritual Intelligence" in the book

'Rewiring the Corporate Brain' in 1997 by Danah Zohar, the concept of spiritual intelligence was introduced. The concept of spiritual intelligence was also suggested by Ken O' Donnel (An Australian author and consultant) in his book 'Endo- Quality- the emotional and spiritual aspects of living person in associations'. Howard Gardner who gave the theory of multiple intelligence and because of the challenges of codifying quantifiable scientific criteria he did not include spiritual intelligence among

his 'eight intelligences'. But he suggested 'existential intelligence'. Gardner's peers replied with research that project existential thinking as indispensable to spirituality. Regarding the definition of spiritual intelligence on matters related to meaning, Zohar and Marshall (2000) described spiritual intelligence as the ability which helps us in addressing and solving issues of significance and value, the Intelligence which help us in placing our deeds and our journey of being alive in a broad, valuable and meaningful context.

General Intelligence : The nature of intelligence has long been a subject of debate in psychology. While psychologists strive to measure intelligence and educators seek to nurture it, there remains no universally agreed-upon definition. Intelligence is considered a behavior-determining attribute, inferred from an individual's actions.

General intelligence refers to the capability to comprehend views, assess circumstances, and resolve issues. It is commonly assessed via different intelligence evaluations, and ongoing study continues to refine these assessments. Psychologists have identified multiple cognitive competences that contribute to intelligence, consisting of:

- Verbal Intelligence
- Visual - Spatial Intelligence
- Literal Reasoning
- Logical Reasoning

General intelligence is a strong indicator of a child's current academic abilities and school performance. Also known as the g-factor, general intelligence represents a broad cognitive capacity that influences ability across various mental challenges. The notion of overall cognitive ability was first proposed by Charles Spearman in 1904, who proposed that a common factor underlies various intellectual abilities. Investigating the link between spiritual intelligence and general intelligence among undergraduate students holds significance for their holistic development, academic performance, well-being, career readiness diversity and inclusion and the advancement of knowledge in relevant disciplines.

The Review of Related Studies is crucial in identifying research problems, establishing theoretical foundations, and refining methodology. Initially, it clarifies concepts and guides research design, while later, it enriches knowledge, integrates findings with existing literature, and enables comparison with previous studies.

Terzi, Gocen and Kaya (2020) conducted a study on 343 teachers to examine the influence of spiritual leadership on organizational trust. The study concluded that spiritual leadership significantly influences organizational trust, primarily through altruistic love, hope, faith, and commitment. It emphasized that leaders play a key role in fostering trust and shaping the organization's value system, particularly in schools, by establishing core values and ensuring member inclusion.

Mufti et. al. (2019) examined the link between spiritual intelligence and professional quality of life among 150 teachers and administrative staff at the University of Gujrat, Pakistan. Using the SISRI-24 and Pro QOL scales, the study found a strong positive correlation between spiritual intelligence and professional well-being. It highlighted spiritual intelligence as a key factor in guiding others and enhancing overall professional well-being.

Makris, N., Tachmatzidis, D., Kazi, S., Spanoud, G. (2019) studied the link between academic performance and cognition in students aged 9 to 15. Using structural equation modeling, they found that cognitive and language abilities strongly predicted school performance, with cognitive flexibility and working memory being key from 9 to 11, while reasoning and language dominated from 13 to 15. Self-evaluation influenced academic performance only in secondary school, with reasoning playing a major role. SES impacted school achievement beyond cognitive factors. The study highlighted the long-term association between intelligence and educational attainment.

Pont, A, Du., Karbin. Z., Rhee, S.H., Corley, R.P., Hewitt, J.K., Friedman, N. P.(2020) explored the link between rumination and intelligence, analyzing brooding and reflective pondering while controlling for depression. Studying 751 participants, they found reflective pondering positively correlated with verbal and performance intelligence, while brooding showed no link. After taking this review of available research studies, it is evident that there are numerous studies on spiritual intelligence and general intelligence which gives an idea about the significance to study this topic.

Statement of the Problem

“To Study the Relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and General Intelligence of Undergraduate Students.”

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the spiritual intelligence of undergraduate male students.
2. To examine the spiritual intelligence of undergraduate female students.
3. To examine the general intelligence of undergraduate male students.
4. To examine the general intelligence of undergraduate female students.
5. To examine the connection between spiritual intelligence and general intelligence of undergraduate male students.
6. To examine the connection between spiritual intelligence and general intelligence of undergraduate female students.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and general intelligence of undergraduate male students.
2. There is no significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and general intelligence of undergraduate female students.

Delimitations of the Study

1. The study was delimited to Saharanpur district only.
2. Only one tool is used for measuring Spiritual Intelligence.
3. Only one tool is used for measuring General Intelligence.

Research Method Used

The investigator selects the most suitable method for the study based on the research problem. Research quality depends on both the design and methodology. This study employs the **Descriptive Survey Method**, which examines existing conditions to determine their nature and extent.

Sample and Sampling Technique

In the current research, **Random Probability Sampling** approach is used. The investigator has taken the list of colleges from Maa Shakumbhari University Saharanpur. From this list two colleges were selected blind foldedly. The researcher went to these colleges and distributed the tests to 50 students of J.V.Jain College and 50 students of Gochar Mahavidyalaya randomly from class registers given by the class teachers of Undergraduate classes.

Variables

Variables used in this study are :

Independent Variable: In the present study Spiritual Intelligence is the independent variable.

Dependent Variable: In the current research General Intelligence is the dependent variable.

Tools Used for the Study

The tool was utilized for data collection:

1. ‘Test of General Intelligence for college students’ by Misra and Pal (2007).
2. ROQAN Spiritual Intelligence for measuring spiritual intelligence by Prof. Roquiya Zauddin and Ms. Anjum Ahmed.

Statistical Technique Used in the Study

Correlation examines the relationship between data groups and quantifies its strength numerically. Pearson’s correlation coefficient measures the relationship linking two variables by computing their

covariance as a fraction of the product of their standard deviations.. Product moment correlation (r) was used to study the effect of one variable on other.

Result

Hypothesis: (i) There is no significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and general intelligence of male students.

A Pearsons coefficient of correlation has been computed between two variables Table No.1 shows that general intelligence of male students is not significantly correlated with spiritual intelligence as the value of coefficients of correlation 'r' comes to be .0568

Table No.-1 : Coefficient of correlation between general intelligence and spiritual intelligence of male students

Gender	Size of Sample	Coefficient of Correlation(r)
Male	50	0.0568

The null hypothesis thus has been accepted and it has been concluded that the relationship between general intelligence and spiritual intelligence of male students is not significantly correlated which means the general intelligence of males does not affect the spiritual intelligence of males or vice-versa.

Hypothesis: (ii) There is no significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and general intelligence of female students.

A Pearsons coefficient of correlation has been computed between two variables. Table no. 2 shows that the general intelligence of girls significantly correlated with spiritual intelligence as the value of coefficient of correlation 'r' comes to be **0.202**

Table No.-2 : Coefficient of correlation between general intelligence and spiritual intelligence of female students.

Gender	Size of Sample	Coefficient of Correlation(r)
Female	50	0.202

The null hypothesis thus has been rejected and it has been concluded that the relationship between the general intelligence and spiritual intelligence of girls is significantly correlated in positive direction, which means that general intelligence of girls affects the spiritual intelligence of girls. It means if girls general intelligence is high then it will be moderately affect on her spiritual intelligence or vice versa.

Conclusion and Discussion

Conclusion(i): The relationship between general intelligence and spiritual intelligence of boys is not significantly correlated which indicate that the general intelligence of boys does not affect the spiritual intelligence of boys or vice versa.

Conclusion(ii): The relationship between general intelligence and spiritual intelligence of girls is significant in positive direction which indicates that general intelligence affects spiritual intelligence.

On the basis of above conclusion, it may be inferred that there existed positive and significant correlation between general intelligence and spiritual intelligence of girls and no significant correlation between general intelligence and spiritual intelligence of boys.

References

1. Arune, P.K. 2006. "Process outcomes in science and extension" Journal of Educational Research and Extension, 43(1): 34-42. Chatterji, P.S. 1983. "A comparative study of personality,

- intelligence and achievement motivation of students in different academic groups" Ph.D. Thesis (Education), Patna University. In M.B. Buch (Ed.), Fourth survey of research in education, Vol. I (1983-88), NCERT, New Delhi, pp. 351-352.
2. Cherry, K. (2023) What Is General Intelligence (G Factor)? <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-general-intelligence-2795210>
 3. Mittal, K. (2017). A Study of General Intelligence among Degree College Students. An Int. J. of Education and Applied Social Science, 8(3):775-779 <https://ndpublisher.in/admin/issues/EQv8no3n.pdf>
 4. Gloria, L., & Vadhera R.P. (2020). The Relationship between General Intelligence (Gi) And Academic Achievement (Aa) In Collegiate Students. Vivek Research e-journal 4(1) http://vivekresearchjournal.org/current_issue/njune2020/2.pdf
 - Henry, E.G. (2019). Statistics in Psychology and Education. Surjeet Publication.
 - Lokesh, K. (2009). Methodology of Educational Research (4th Edition). Vikas Publication House Pvt Ltd
 5. Mangal, S.K. (2019). Statistics in Psychology and Education (2nd Edition). PHI Learning Private Limited
 6. Mangal, S.K., & Shubhra, M. (2020). Research Methodology in Behavioural Sciences. PHI Learning Private Limited.
 7. Zohar, D., & Marshall, I. (2000). SQ - Spiritual intelligence, the ultimate intelligence. USA, New York, NY, Bloom Burg. 2000; 15-18
 8. Vaughan, F. (2002). Journal of Humanistic Psychology. Vol. 42 (2), 16-33. Wigglesworth, C. (2012). The twenty-one skills of spiritual intelligence. Select books, Inc, New York
 9. Pant, N., & Srivastava, S. K. (2014). Effect of spiritual intelligence on mental health and quality of life among college students. Zenith International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research. ISSN 2231-5780 Vol.4 (8), 208-215

